

Future calculator

Divakar Mani

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E-mail: divakar@live.in

Abstract

To take groundwater using a submersible pump, the borehole is drilled using a diesel air compressor. This process is cost-consuming and the concept of future calculator was worked out in a difficult situation to prevent loss for the owner by predicting the diesel air compressor's future results. For borehole drilling applications, future results prediction will be helpful in analysing the performance of the diesel air compressor, the geological formation and the drilling cost estimation based on time.

Keywords: future prediction, performance analysis, geological formation analysis, cost estimation.

1. Introduction

The prediction about the future is possible using mathematics when calculations are based on time. Necessities are developed as applications and their results are the needs. The results of an application depend on the performance of the system and future results prediction will be helpful to troubleshoot system errors in advance.

2. Concept of future calculator

Figure 1: Overview of future calculator^[1]

Based on time, the concept to calculate the future was developed using a borehole drilling application in which the future result is calculated using past and present results. Event occurs at a time and the time interval between the events might be regular or irregular depending upon requirements which are then averaged as time intervals average. At event time, each event produces its own result and the interval result is the difference in event results. These interval results are averaged to find the interval results average. To predict the future result, the interval results average difference is added to or subtracted from the present result. The difference is added when past interval results are linearly increasing and subtracted when past interval results are linearly decreasing.^[1]

The obtained future result is only a prediction at that particular time and may vary over a period of time due to the change in system performance.^[1]

In short, the concept can be written as

$$\text{Future result} = \text{Present result} \pm \text{Interval results average}^{[1]}$$

2.1. Event time

The time (t) of the event (e_n) is event time (et_n). Event time (et_n) has past time (at), present time (pt) and future time (FT).^[1]

2.2. Time interval

The time interval (ti_n) is defined as the difference in event time (et_n) and it might be regular or irregular.^{[1][2]}

$$ti_n = et_{n+1} - et_n \quad (1)$$

2.3. Time intervals average

The time intervals average (ti_{avg}) is defined as the ratio of the sum of the selected time intervals (ti_n) to the total number of selected data (m).^{[1][2]}

$$ti_{avg} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} ti_n}{m} \quad (2)$$

2.4. Event result

The result produced by an application at event time (et_n) is event result (er_n). Event results (er_n) have past results (ar), present results (pr) and future results (FR).^[1]

2.5. Interval result

The interval result (ir_n) is defined as the difference in event results (er_n).^{[1][2]}

$$ir = er_{max} - er_{min} \quad (3)$$

For linearly increasing event results (er_n), use equation (3a) to calculate interval result (ir_n).^{[1][2]}

$$ir_n = er_{n+1} - er_n \quad (3a)$$

For linearly decreasing event results (er_n), use equation (3b) to calculate interval result (ir_n).^{[1][2]}

$$ir_n = er_n - er_{n+1} \quad (3b)$$

2.6. Interval results average

The interval results average (ir_{avg}) is defined as the ratio of the sum of the selected interval results (ir_n) to the total number of selected data (m).^{[1][2]}

$$ir_{avg} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} ir_n}{m} \quad (4)$$

2.7. Future result

The future result (FR) at the time (pt+ti_{avg}) [i.e. FR(pt+ti_{avg})] can be calculated in minutes by adding or subtracting interval results average (ir_{avg}) difference with the present result (pr). If past interval results (ir_n) are linearly increasing, then the interval results average (ir_{avg}) difference is added to the present result (pr) and if past interval results (ir_n) are linearly decreasing, then the interval results average (ir_{avg}) difference is subtracted from the present result (pr).^{[1][2]}

The performance of the system has an impact on application results and so the obtained future result is valid only at that time and may vary later.^{[1][2]}

$$FR(pt + ti_{avg}) = pr \pm ir_{avg} \tag{5}$$

3. Application - Air compressor for drilling

Nowadays submersible pump is used to take groundwater for residential and agricultural use. This can be achieved by drilling a borehole using a skid mounted diesel air compressor fitted in a truck. Chicago Pneumatic skid mounted CPS550-200 RIG diesel air compressor was used for borehole drilling and calculations were made using drilled RPM and drilled depth to predict future results for troubleshooting system errors in advance.

Figure 2: Skid mounted CPS550-200 RIG fitted in a truck

Parameters	Details
Air flow (cfm) / Working pressure (psig)	550 / 200
Engine - Make / Model / HP / Max speed (rpm)	Ashok Leyland / AL UW6DTI / 205 / 2100
Fuel tank capacity(l) / Oil capacity (l)	190 / 35
Skid mounted [L x W x H] (mm) / Dry weight (kg)	2985 x 1504 x 1919 / 1890

Table 1: Parameters of skid mounted CPS550-200 RIG

3.1. Calculations using RPM

Past and present drilled RPM (r_n) details are used in calculations to predict future results of drilled RPM (FR_{rpm}) at event time (et_n).

3.1.1. Future RPM prediction

For a single event (e_n), drilled RPM (r_n) at any event time (et_n) can be defined as the difference in present RPM (p_{rpm}) and start RPM (s_{rpm}).

$$r_n = p_{rpm} - s_{rpm} \quad (6)$$

Event result - Average drilling RPM is the event result (er_n) at event time (et_n) and it's defined as the ratio of the drilled depth (d_n) to the drilled RPM (r_n).

$$er_n = \frac{d_n}{r_n} \quad (7)$$

Interval result - Past event results (er_n) are linearly decreasing and so equation (3b) is used to calculate interval result (ir_n).

Interval results average - Equation (4) is used to calculate the interval results average (ir_{avg}).

Future result - Based on equation (5), future result of drilled RPM (FR_{rpm}) at the time ($pt+ti_{avg}$) [i.e. $FR_{rpm}(pt+ti_{avg})$] can be calculated in minutes by subtracting interval results average (ir_{avg}) difference from the present result of average drilling RPM (pr_{a-rpm}).

$$FR_{rpm}(pt+ti_{avg}) = pr_{a-rpm} - ir_{avg} \quad (8)$$

3.1.2. Air compressor performance analysis using RPM

The system performance of the CPS550-200 diesel air compressor can be observed using drilled RPM (r_n) linearity over a period of time. For this, a linear performance plot is made as a function of event time (et_n) Vs drilled RPM (r_n).

3.1.3. Geological formation analysis using RPM

The hardness of geological formation can be analysed using RPM (FR_{rpm-g}) based on time. For RPM-based analysis, drilled RPM (r_n) is used in calculations.

Event result - Drilled RPM (r_n) is considered as the event result (er_n) for geological formation analysis using RPM (FR_{rpm-g}) at event time (et_n).

Interval result - Past event results (er_n) are linearly increasing and so equation (3a) is used to calculate interval result (ir_n).

Interval results average - Equation (4) is used to calculate the interval results average (ir_{avg}).

Future result - Based on equation (5), future result of the geological formation using RPM (FR_{rpm-g}) at the time ($pt+ti_{avg}$) [i.e. $FR_{rpm-g}(pt+ti_{avg})$] can be calculated in minutes by adding interval results average (ir_{avg}) difference to the present result of drilled RPM (pr_{r-rpm}).

$$FR_{rpm-g}(pt+ti_{avg}) = pr_{r-rpm} + ir_{avg} \quad (9)$$

The future results difference (FR_{dif}) is the difference in future results ($FR(pt+ti_{avg})$) and it can be implemented as like equation (3).

$$FR_{dif} = FR_{max} - FR_{min} \quad (10)$$

If future results difference (FR_{dif}) of drilled RPM (r_n) increases with time (t) then the hardness of geological formation increases and vice versa.

3.1.4. Cost estimation using RPM

The total expenditure to drill a borehole using a diesel air compressor can be estimated using drilled RPM (r_n).

Based on equation (5), the total cost to drill a borehole can be estimated using RPM (FR_{rpm-c}) at the time ($pt+ti_{avg}$) [i.e. $FR_{rpm-c}(pt+ti_{avg})$] in minutes by adding interval results average (ir_{avg}) difference to the present result of drilled RPM (pr_{rpm}) and multiplying it with the price per RPM.

$$FR_{rpm-c}(pt+ti_{avg}) = (pr_{rpm} + ir_{avg}) \times Price \text{ per RPM} \quad (11)$$

3.2. Calculations using depth

Past and present drilled depth (d_n) details are used in calculations to predict future results of drilled depth (FR_{depth}) at event time (et_n).

3.2.1. Future depth prediction

Event result - Drilled depth (d_n) is the event result (er_n) at event time (et_n).

$$er_n = d_n \quad (12)$$

Interval result - Past event results (er_n) are linearly increasing and so equation (3a) is used to calculate interval result (ir_n).

Interval results average - Equation (4) is used to calculate the interval results average (ir_{avg}).

Future result - Based on equation (5), future result of drilled depth (FR_{depth}) at the time ($pt+ti_{avg}$) [i.e. $FR_{depth}(pt+ti_{avg})$] can be calculated in minutes by adding interval results average (ir_{avg}) difference to the present result of drilled depth ($pr_{d-depth}$).

$$FR_{depth}(pt+ti_{avg}) = pr_{d-depth} + ir_{avg} \quad (13)$$

3.2.2. Air compressor performance analysis using depth

The system performance of the CPS550-200 diesel air compressor can be observed using drilled depth (d_n) linearity over a period of time. For this, a linear performance plot is made as a function of event time (et_n) Vs drilled depth (d_n).

3.2.3. Geological formation analysis using depth

The hardness of geological formation can be analysed using depth ($FR_{depth-g}$) based on time. For depth-based analysis, drilled depth (d_n) is used in calculations.

Equation (13) is used to calculate future result of the geological formation using depth ($FR_{depth-g}$) at the time ($pt+ti_{avg}$) [i.e. $FR_{depth-g}(pt+ti_{avg})$].

Based on equation (10), if future results difference (FR_{dif}) of drilled depth (d_n) decreases with time (t) then the hardness of geological formation increases and vice versa.

3.2.4. Cost estimation using depth

The total expenditure to drill a borehole using a diesel air compressor can be estimated using drilled depth (d_n).

Based on equation (5), the total cost to drill a borehole can be estimated using depth ($FR_{depth-c}$) at the time ($pt+ti_{avg}$) [i.e. $FR_{depth-c}(pt+ti_{avg})$] in minutes by adding interval results average (ir_{avg}) difference to the present result of drilled depth ($pr_{d-depth}$) and multiplying it with the price per feet.

$$FR_{depth-c}(pt+ti_{avg}) = (pr_{d-depth} + ir_{avg}) \times \text{Price per feet} \quad (14)$$

4. Conclusion

Future results of borehole drilling application was predicted based on the time using calculations and the properties were analysed. Similarly, the concept of future calculator can be used in other applications too.

References

[1] Francis A. Jenkins and Harvey E. White, "Fundamentals of Optics", McGraw Hill Education (India) Private Limited, ISBN 978-1-25-900229-8, 2011.

[2] Naftaly Menn, "Practical Optics", Academic Press, ISBN 9798181476455, 2004.

Abbreviations

$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \infty$; t: Time; e_n : Events; et_n : Event time; at: Past time; pt: Present time; FT: Future time; ti_n : Time intervals; ti_{avg} : Time intervals average; m: Total number of selected data; er_n : Event results; ar: Past results; pr: Present results; FR: Future results; ir_n : Interval results; er_{max} : Event result with maximum value; er_{min} : Event result with minimum value; ir_{avg} : Interval results average; r_n : Drilled RPM; FR_{rpm} : Future results of drilled RPM; p_{rpm} : Present RPM; s_{rpm} : Start RPM; d_n : Drilled depth; pr_{a-rpm} : Present result of average drilling RPM; pr_{r-rpm} : Present result of drilled RPM; FR_{rpm-g} : Geological formation analysis using RPM; FR_{dif} : Difference in future results; FR_{max} : Future result with maximum value; FR_{min} : Future result with minimum value; FR_{rpm-c} : Cost estimation using RPM; FR_{depth} : Future results of drilled depth; $pr_{d-depth}$: Present result of drilled depth; $FR_{depth-g}$: Geological formation analysis using depth; $FR_{depth-c}$: Cost estimation using depth.

About the author

Divakar Mani studied Smart Systems with Microsystems Engineering as a specialisation at Hochschule Furtwangen and received his M.Sc. in 2015. He is working on application development, product deployment and solution finding in the field of Microsystems Engineering, Communication Systems and History.

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